

Stylistic Aspects of Advertising Posters in the Soviet Union

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Abstract: This article examines Soviet social, political, and moralizing posters. The textual and visual images of Soviet poster-making with their thematic meanings are explored, and the role of poster creativity in forming the moral and ethical qualities of the younger generation is analyzed. Results suggest that the Soviet poster becomes a means of communication, as with the help of an image and text, it seeks to convey to the reader the main ethical values of Soviet ideology. At the same time, the importance of both verbal and non-verbal images is relevant. The importance of style in creating a visual image is emphasized, and conclusions are drawn about the importance of Soviet culture and its display in the language, poetry, and visual image of posters produced in the Soviet Union.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Sovyet ideolojisi
Poster
Görsel imge
Gençlik kültürü
Ahlaki değer

Sovyetler Birliği'nde Reklam Posterlerinin Deyişbilimsel Yönleri

Özet: Bu çalışmada Sovyetler Birliği'nde üretilmiş olan reklam posterlerinin toplumsal, siyasi ve ahlaki göndermeleri deyişbilim açısından incelenmektedir. Çalışmada, posterlerde yer alan sözlü ve görsel imgeler Sovyetler Birliği'nde baskın olan poster geleneği üzerinden deyişbilimsel bir okumaya tabi tutulmaktadır. Çalışmada, dönemin posterlerinin tematik yönelimi araştırılmakta ve poster yaratıcılığının genç neslin ahlaki ve etik niteliklerini oluşturmadaki işlevleri kayıt altına alınmaktadır. Çalışmanın sonuçları bizlere Sovyet siyasetinin posterleri birer iletişim aracı haline getirdiğinin altını çizirken bir imge ve metin yardımıyla okuyucuya Sovyet ideolojisinin temel etik değerlerinin aktarılmasının amaçlandığını da ortaya koymaktadır ki sözlü ve görsel imgelerin önemi bu noktada belirginleşmektedir. Çalışmanın sonuçlarıyla birlikte görsel imgenin yaratılmasında üslubun önemi vurgulanmakta, Sovyetler Birliği'nde üretilen afişlerin dilinde, Sovyet kültürünün yansımaları görülmektedir.

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1. Introduction

People with high moral standards are believed to do the right from an ethical point of view while they are expected to instruct others, set an example for them, and convey the importance of establishing high morals in society (Yovanovich, 2024; Krylova *et al.*, 2020). Although it is generally accepted that individuals have different approaches to and standards of morals, it is univocally accepted that apart from this individual aspect of morality, its social character makes it even more complex to decipher.

Among many social aspects that frame individual and social morals, political and religious issues shape morals more than any other factor. Throughout history, religious and political power groups have shaped what is acceptable, necessary, and essential in society, often printing materials to spread their views on pressing social, political, and cultural issues. Declarations, pamphlets, wars in American history, and posters during election campaigns are among the most popular print materials that functioned as ideological tools to spread societal viewpoints.

The Soviet era (1922-1991) was one of human history's most influential historical, geographical, and political periods. The political system was fully authoritarian and highly centralized, and the economic foundation was characterized by the Socialist ownership of the means of production, distribution, and exchange as the economy of the entire country was controlled by a series of five-year plans that set targets for all forms of production (Conquest *et al.*, 2024). During this era, the Soviet ideology was aimed to be spread mainly through print materials, among which posters were the leading ones, as poster-making aimed to develop Soviet citizens' moral and ethical qualities. The orientation of the posters was related to the ideology and political course of the country. In addition, immortal and universal techniques, slogans, and visual images played a significant role in creating posters as they served as powerful tools that aimed to shape public opinion. As with other tools of advertising and informing, social advertising through posters affected citizens' emotional and mental states, affecting their moral and ethical value systems.

In essence, social advertising aims to change public behavior while drawing attention to shared social and political problems that threaten the political system by and large. The primary function of such advertising is to appeal to a person's inner consciousness, morals and ethical values. It is no secret that for a long time, it has been one of the factors in forming a person's personality; it penetrates into a person's consciousness and influences the further perception of the world. As posters make use of visual as well as textual imprints, they are believed to leave a vivid mark in a person's memory, in a way to lead this personal activity in a certain direction, often towards a mass belief system.

In particular, the Soviet system is argued to have used posters as instruments of war:

The Soviet war posters are primarily designed for the homefront, where people can almost comprehend the posters without the explanation of the captions. The text of the captions consists of either a verse, a war communique, or a phrase from the order of the day of the Supreme Commander-in-Chief, or a slogan for a placard on May Day. The citizens are well informed on the current events pertaining to their interests and are at home with their historical background and personages. For foreign consumption, however, the commentary of the captions is quite useful, although the pictorial part of the poster eloquently and vividly presents its idea (Novossiltzeff, 1941, p. 70).

One of the main ideologists in the fight against corruption was the poet Mayakovsky (1959), who wrote the poem "Bribery Takers." In essence, Mayakovsky's poetic message is clear: He

cannot come to terms with bribe-takers who will destroy the country with its glorious revolution. At the same time, the human hand served as a vital image symbol in Communist propaganda. The image of the red hand, invented by Mayakovsky, is used in his poetry and posters and is interpreted as signaling punishment, power, justice, and retribution. In any case, the red hand represents the citizens, workers, and the Communist Party. Thus, the image of the hand is central to the Soviet state's fight against corruption, as seen in a series of posters used during that era. Among many, Mayakovsky's innovative hand symbolized the state's fight against corruption. It became famous through various posters hanging around the communist state— such textual and visual images required all citizens to be informed about social evils.

In this article, we examine Soviet posters dedicated to morality, spiritual values, and socio-political problems and try to trace precisely how they aimed to influence personality formation. This research seeks to identify the posters' main themes and determine their roles in forming correct foundations and eradicating vices, particularly corruption. In Soviet times, the most significant emphasis was placed on creating a person's internal qualities through the education of the younger generation. These messages were addressed to children and adolescents who were to form a stratum of society with morally correct attributes in the future.

1.1. Problem Statement

Visuals are often regarded as capable of “representing the world in a cloak of apparent authenticity” (Alvaray, 2014, p. 109). This is primarily due to their dual role as resources and mediators, working alongside language to shape and convey ideas (Radley, 2010, p. 268). As carriers of rich semiotic and cultural meanings, visuals function as culture-laden artefacts, offering condensed representations of sociocultural realities (Zorba, 2020). With all these in mind, this study aims to identify significant themes in Soviet-era posters by tracing how Soviet posters influenced the formation of a personality because, in Soviet times, the most important emphasis was on forming a person's internal qualities with morally correct attributes.

1.2. Research Questions

This study tried to answer the following research questions:

1. Which moral messages are typical of Soviet-era posters?
2. How do Soviet posters try to influence personality formation?
3. What caricature images can be identified in the posters?

2. Methods

To find answers to the research questions set, we conducted a qualitative stylistic analysis of visual and textual elements of posters printed and used during the Soviet era. “Stylistic analysis in linguistics refers to the identification of patterns of usage in speech and writing” (Arikan, 2015, p. 126) and “requires a thorough understanding of how properties of language (semantics, syntactic, morphological, etc.) work in literature” (Arikan & Zorba, 2015, p. 140). In this study, a systematic comparative stylistic approach was followed to analyze the particularities of the materials more deeply.

Alderson and Short (1989) define stylistics as a method that “is intended to help determine interpretation through the examination of what a text contains, by describing the linguistic devices an author has used, and the effects produced by such devices. Such an analysis is predominantly text-based and has tended to see texts as containing meanings” (p. 72). Thus,

similar studies indicate that “certain linguistic features which are stylistically significant and therefore foregrounded through register, lexis, deviation, parallelism and metaphor” (Timuçin, 2010, p. 131) are taken into consideration in the stylistic analysis of the contents of the posters selected for the analysis. For this study, the researchers analysed the selected posters, first individually noting their findings. Then, they compared their findings (85% interrater reliability in the first phase) and reached a consensus in finalizing their results. Throughout this data analytical process, units of analysis were decided for visual and textual elements that make up the posters as “These units serve as linguistic tools to express value judgments or convey opinions, presenting a nuanced evaluative dimension” (Shintemirova *et al.*, 2024, p. 175).

3. Results

The major quality of the posters analyzed is that they are instructive in nature. In simplest terms, these posters aim to instruct children to help them form an understanding of what is good and bad (evil). Further analyses revealed that these posters aim to nurture in them the following qualities: independence (Figure 1), respect for elders (Figures 2, 3), care for younger ones (Figure 4), hard work and dedication (Figure 5, 6, 7), and honesty (Figure 8). In Figure 3, the poster’s message is clear: “You and I have to help mom with the housework ourselves,” the elderly (bigger) boy tells the younger (smaller) brother. These posters highlight the relationship between the older and younger generations in a way that frames their life experiences with certain morals. The content of these posters suggests that they glorify experiences withheld by the elderly while treating the younger generation as miniature adults who require guidance and advice.

Figure 1. Learn to do everything yourself!

Figure 2. Do not be like that!

Figure 3. Help your elders!

Figure 4. Do not offend the kid!

Figure 5. Get excellent marks!

Figure 6. Are not you like that?

Figure 7. To have more, one should produce more. To produce more, one should know more.

Figure 8. Never tell a lie!

In Soviet times, responsibility for educating the younger generation partly lay with the state. Thus, from birth, children understand the values of life, try to live up to moral ideals, and

also become role models. Of course, we can say that such a contribution from the state was necessary and was a great success.

In addition, the Soviet poster reflected some problems that require solutions to eradicate such social illnesses as alcoholism, smoking, hooliganism, and corruption, mainly through accepting a bribe. In Figure 11, the Soviet state's protection of the child from alcoholism is observable in which the hand's gesture functions to stop the consumption of alcohol. In Figure 12, the poster read: "Tobacco is poison," followed by the order that completes the poster's overall message: Give up smoking! As these texts suggest, the Soviet poster-making activity made use of direct statements followed by exclamation marks in a simple language that can be understood by all of the literature and semi-literate citizens.

Besides the posters' textual properties, images play a significant role in poster-making. Figures 13 and 14 portray the citizens who use their hands to complete the symbolic action supported by the textual cues. Regardless of what the contents of these posters suggest, it should be noted that all these posters push the individual towards accepting what the state asks them to, suggesting that citizens' choices will inevitably affect the state's existence as a healthy, unified entity. Thus, it can be inferred that alcohol use, smoking, attachment to certain movements or sports, and bribery signify poor morals that eradicate the citizen and, thus, the state. Again, there is a commanding voice in all these posters, as seen with the exclamation marks used to tell people what to do and what not to do.

Figure 11. Not a single drop!

Figure 12. Give up smoking!

Figure 13. Fight hooliganism!

Figure 14. He has learned one science- how to accept a bribe more accurately.

In addition, the Soviet poster promoted family values- a unified, strong, and happy family that is fundamental to the Communist cause (Figure 15). The baby, held in the strong arms and hands of the father, is happily holding the Communist flag. It should be noted that the poster's textual content signifies the equivalence of the child with the family: "In favor of a joyful, flourishing childhood! In favor of a happy, close-knit family! Thus, it is also implied that the family's *raison d'être* is growing children who will pick the Communist flag up, as the visual content of the poster shows. Needless to say, all the family members have worn red and white, exactly like the flag's colors, suggesting that they exist as and for the communist existence.

Figure 15. In favor of a joyful, flourishing childhood! In favor of a happy, close-knit family!

4. Conclusion

This study found that posters from the Soviet era highlight the relationship between the older and younger generations through certain morals attached to them. The content of these posters suggests that they glorify experiences withheld by the elderly while treating the younger generation as miniature adults who require guidance and advice. The Soviet poster reflects the most important moral qualities, emphasizes family values, and shows the importance of maintaining a healthy lifestyle, not becoming a negative example, and trying to maintain your health. Most often, exclamatory constructions are used in the slogans, including the imperative mood of the verb: “Learn to do everything yourself!” “Get excellent marks!”, “Don’t offend your elders!”, “Don’t hit the child,” “Help the younger ones!” In addition, exclamatory negative constructions are common: “Not a single drop!”, “No!”

This study has limitations. One limitation is its focus on a single system, the Soviet Union. Posters are prepared and used worldwide for communication. Thus, comparative studies are needed to decipher how posters were used in various political systems around the globe and identify commonalities and differences. Also, the study focused on the visual and verbal images from a stylistic perspective. Hence, employing the views of different schools of criticism would bring different perspectives to the material at hand.

In conclusion, poster art is one of the methods for developing a person’s moral and ethical qualities from an early age. The thematic focus of the poster is connected not only with ideology but also with the country’s political course. Ideology helps emphasize negative qualities through images that instill correct and accurate dogmas in a person, subsequently shaping the personality. Social advertising, as can be seen in the making of the Soviet posters, is an effective way to influence a person, as it affects the emotional and mental component of a person, makes him or her think about essential and global things, and, in some cases, sees himself or herself from the outside and decides to change.

Note on Ethical Issues

The authors confirm that the study does not need ethics committee approval according to the research integrity rules in their country (Date of Confirmation: 26/03/2024).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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